

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY ON EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION AND JOB SATISFACTION

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the application of Social Exchange Theory (SET) in organizational behavior, reviewing the literature by focusing on its definitions, contexts (both social and economic), current variables, applications, limitations, and its impact on job satisfaction and motivation. SET, developed by Homans and elaborated upon by Blau, explains social interactions based on exchanges of benefits and costs between individuals or parties. It encompasses both economic exchanges, governed by formal contracts and monitoring, and social exchanges, characterized by trust and flexibility. The theory finds application in various organizational contexts such as employee relationships, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction. Contemporary studies continue to validate SET's relevance by integrating new variables like work-life balance and flexible work arrangements. Despite its utility, SET faces challenges, notably in diverse cultural settings where its applicability may vary. The article also examines SET's influence on motivation, distinguishing between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and its role in shaping job satisfaction. While SET offers insights into these areas, it does not predict individual behaviors conclusively. Future research could further explore the causal relationships between SET variables and organizational outcomes. This comprehensive review underscores SET's broad applicability in understanding and managing organizational dynamics while acknowledging its limitations in predicting human behavior outright.

Keywords: Social Exchange Theory, Employee Motivation, Job Satisfaction.

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INTRODUCTION

Research in the field of organizational behaviour has been undertaken to find strategies and best practices for improving organizational techniques that support the efficient running of an organization. One of the most useful theories to analyse organizational behaviour is social exchange theory (SET) (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005 cited in Ahmed et al., 2023). Social exchange theory is a very widespread occurrence that permeates all aspects of everyday life. Not only do we exchange with our companies, but we also subtly interact with our family, friends, and relatives. In the first part of this article, the Social Exchange Theory (SET) will be defined in both social and more focus on the economic context, current variables of SET, applications, and limitations of the theory. Secondly, the impact of SET on job satisfaction and motivation will be discussed.

Social Exchange Theory

Social exchange theory (SET), as defined by Homans (1950, cited in Lawler & Thye, 2006), can explain any social activity through undertaken activities, the interaction between individuals, and developed sentiments between each person. Sentiments are human internal statutes, such as liking\disliking (Lawler & Thye, 2006). While Homans focused on introducing the psychological part of SET Blau highlighted the economic part of the theory (Ahmad et al., 2023). SET can be a series of continuous benefits between parties (Shore et al., 2007 cited in Wikhamn & Hall, 2012). For instance, an employee counts the benefits from his job over the costs if benefits have been over the costs, it is profits and leads to more exchange. The exchange in SET contains sources of exchange, which can be financial or emotional sources (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003 in Wikhamn & Hall, 2012), even explicit or implicit (Ahmad et al., 2023). The sources give a strong social relationship if it is valuable for both partners (Eisenberger, et al., 2001 cited in Wikhamn & Hall, 2012). SET predicts that initiating social exchange with good intentions leads to a target response of increased good action and decreased negative action (Cropanzano, 2017).

SET: Analysis of Individual and Party Exchanges

SET, analysis of both individuals as well as parties exchange. Ahmad et al., (2023) stated that most of the SET literature explains the relationship between organizations and individuals such as customers, employees, and suppliers (Moorman et al., 1998; Houston et al., 1992; Perrone et al., 2003), even though no significant amount of the literature addressed individual to individual exchange in the work context as between peers but many addressed Leader-Member Exchange (LME) (Eisenberger et al., 2004). LME explains how employees feel about the importance of their duties since it leads to advantages received from leaders (Armel et al., 2003 cited in Wikhamn & Hall, 2012); (Gergen, 1969; Gouldner, 1960 cited in Cropanzano, 2017).

SET: Economic Context vs Social Context

SET can explain interaction in both economic and social exchanges. In economic exchange, there are negotiations or formal contracts leading each party to fulfill their obligations in a certain given time (Blau, 1964 cited in Ahmad et al., 2023). In contrast, in the social exchange context, there is no negotiation not provided time to fulfill obligations which can be tangible or intangible, exchange relies more on trust and commitment (Blau, 1964; Emerson, 1981; Molm, 2003 cited in Shore et al., 2009). Furthermore, Economic exchange has less trust and more monitoring compared to social exchange where more trust and flexibility (Organ, 1990 cited in Cropanzano, 2017). Commonly, both social and economic exchange need time to examine the risk-taking in giving resources and waiting for a return (Shore et al., 2009). Table 1 illustrates social and economic transactions. (Ahmad et al., 2023)

Table 1 Social and economic transactions. (Ahmad et al., 2023)

		<u>Type of Transaction</u>	
		Social Transaction	Economic Transaction
<u>Type of Relationship</u>	Social Exchange	<u>Cell-1-Match</u> Social transaction in a social exchange	<u>Cell-2-Mismatch</u> Economic transaction in a social exchange
	Economic Exchange	<u>Cell-3-Mismatch</u> Social transaction in an economic exchange	<u>Cell-4-Match</u> Economic transaction in an economic exchange

SET Applicability to Current Work Variables

Even though SET has been examined in the last century, some studies investigated if SET is still applicable. There are many emerging variables that can be added to assess the exchange such as time-related variables, work-family balance, and flexible working hours (Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018). Moreover, modern management is more decentralized, empowering, and focused on employees and customers (Daft, 2015 cited in Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018). In 2013, a study done in the Scandinavian context involving 400 professional employees indicated that SET is still an applicable obligation feeling a mechanism of reciprocation (Wikhamn & Hall, 2012).

SET Applications

SET is one theory that addresses many varied organizational subjects (Blau, 1964 cited in Liaquat & Mehmood, 2017). For instance, SET can explain organizational behaviours topics: commitment, organizational citizenship behaviors, supervisory, organizational support, and justice (Organ, 1990; Bishop et al., 2000; Ladd & Henry, 2000; Tepper and Taylor, 2003, cited in Ahmad et al., 2023) ;(Organ, 1988; Tepper & Taylor, 2003 cited in Cropanzano, 2017). Moreover, SET explains work outcomes such as Job satisfaction, organization commitment, job performance, and organizational citizenship (Birtch et al., 2016).

There are many applications for SET. It can be used by human resources professionals to understand the relationship between organization initiatives and employee outcomes in return (Wikhamn, & Hall, 2012). For example: a study examining the application of SET across culture suggest that SET can be used in developing relationship between individual and leaders, individual and organization, and group with one or both managers and organization (Shore et al. 2009).

SET Limitations

Nonetheless, some challenges and limitations face SET, including the Varied cultural context is a challenge facing application SET. Agarwal and Bhargava, (2014), stated that the application of SET is not examined in Eastern culture and further research needs to be done. Furthermore, Meta-analysis indicates that there are differences between Western and Western Eastern cultures in terms of the relationship between person to group, person to supervisor, and loyalty to superior (Oh et al., 2014 cited in Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018). Another study indicates that culture is a medium between employer and employee in understanding organizational value and performance precipitation in giving work outcomes in return, creating a mutual interdependent relationship (Wikhamn and Hall, 2012 cited in Liaquat & Mehmood, 2017). Another limitation is, that the complex modern workplace leads to more dimension sophisticated relationships which are difficult to understand (Ahmad et al., 2023). SET succeeds in explaining exchange but does not predicate human behavior. Ahmad et al., (2023) stated that a positive relationship does not certainly lead to positive action in return, for instance, good, initiated action can lead to a negative response driven by jealousy.

Motivation and SET

Motivation is a process that explains the intensity, direction, and persistence of an individual in order to achieve their goals (Deci & Ryan, 2013). However, many people mistakenly perceive motivation as a personal characteristic that is only owned by some, while others do not possess it.

Motivation is the internal process that starts, guides, and sustains an individual's actions and behaviors toward achieving their objectives. It serves as the driving force or psychological trigger that stimulates an individual's desire to take specific actions (Deci & Ryan, 2013).

Motivation can be divided into two main categories - extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic motivation is driven by external factors, such as rewards, recognition, and appreciation. In contrast, intrinsic motivation stems from internal sources, such as the enjoyment and satisfaction an individual feels when performing a task (Amabile, 1993 cited in Hussain et al., 2020). Intrinsic motivation can lead to a sense of accomplishment, self-esteem, and positive feedback, which can fuel an individual's drive to achieve their goals. (Jalagat, 2016).

Motivation can be categorized as either positive or negative. Positive motivation involves an individual putting in significant effort towards a task with the expectation of receiving recognition, affiliation, positive reinforcement, or rewards. For instance, a student might study regularly to achieve high marks, placements, and performance awards. On the other hand, negative motivation involves an individual directing their efforts towards avoiding unwanted circumstances, often by force or out of fear. For example, a student might study to avoid the shame of poor grades within their peer group or scolding from their parents. While positive motivation helps to maintain a feeling of high self-esteem and happiness, negative motivation might create resentment and frustration.

There are many studies that used SET to investigate employee motivation. For instance, in a study to determine the mediating role of intrinsic motivation between abusive supervision of subordinates on workers' psychological wellness, the empirical findings, employees' intention to leave their jobs and psychological well-being are both highly impacted by abusive supervision. In addition, motivation impacts exchange relations and is perhaps one of the main failings of society (Mitchell et al., 2012). It has been noticed that motivation, job satisfaction, and performance are not just interrelated but interdependent (Jalagat, 2016).

Job Satisfaction and SET:

Job satisfaction can be defined as the individual feeling of like or dislike toward their jobs, in other words, job satisfaction can be positive if it perceives employees expectations with the result (McKenna, 2000 cited in Gui et al., 2009). According to Jalagat, there are several factors that influence job satisfaction such as: Financial benefits, leadership, organizational culture, flexible work, and interpersonal communication (2016). Those factors are conceived with different values for each individual as SET analysis.

Job satisfaction is highly important in modern management. A high level of job satisfaction usually leads to high individual productivity and organizational outcomes (Jalagat, 2016). Furthermore, there is a direct link between job satisfaction and performance (Jalagat, 2016). Furthermore, there are mutual dual direction between job satisfaction and life satisfaction (Judge & Watanabe, 1993 cited in Eid, & Larsen, 2008).

An employee who feels that their relationship with their leader is fair in dividing resources will participate in social reward (Eid, & Larsen, 2008) ;(Gui et al., 2009) ;(Deluga, 1994; Konovsky & Pugh, 1994; Pillai et al., 1999 cited in Zeinabadi & Salehi, 2011).

Employee satisfaction and SET, there are many studies that used SET to understand job satisfaction In 2006, a study investigated the relationship between safe work environments and work outcomes using SET to understand it and found that there are mediation roles for job satisfaction between a safe climate between truck drivers and positive work outcomes (Huang et al., 2016). In the previous study, SET analyses varied individual understanding of safe environment perception and how this perception led to employee satisfaction. Another link factor between SET and Job satisfaction is trust. Another study stated that abusive supervision has a negative impact on workers' mental health and job satisfaction in their work, and it is a significant social issue in the workplace (Hussain et al., 2020). Trust is a key element in SET, moreover, it has been linked with job satisfaction and performance (Cropanzano et al., 2017). SET contributes to understanding many topics such as job satisfaction and many others like employee engagement and employee turnover rate (Cropanzano et al., 2017).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, SET is a wide theory for human behaviours. Workers serve as an organization's most significant stakeholders as they are crucial to its success or failure (Liaquat & Mehmood, 2017). In this essay, SET was reviewed in terms of both economic and social context. Current studies added more variables to the theory to adjust the dynamic to the environment. Several studies proved that SET is still applicable. SET is a varied umbrella covering topics such as Job satisfaction, organization commitment, job performance, and organizational citizenship (Birtch et al., 2016). There are many applications for SET. It can be used by human resources professionals to understand the relationship between organization initiatives and employee outcomes in return (Wikhamn, & Hall, 2012). Many studies analyse motivation and job satisfaction through SET, moreover, motivation and job satisfaction have interrelationships, yet the causal relation is not clear, and further investigation can be done. However, some limitations and Challenges face SET such as various cultural contexts, and complex workplaces, and the theory explains yet does not predict behaviours.

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